

Base catalysed addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene in aqueous acetonitrile – A kinetic study^ψ

P. A. Sarathi, A. Vijayakumar, C. Gnanasekaran and A. Shunmugasundaram*

Research Department of Chemistry, VHNSN College, Virudhunagar-626 001, India

E-mail : shunmuge@hotmail.com

Manuscript received 11 October 2004

The kinetics of nucleophilic addition of thiophenol (PhSH) to β -nitrostyrene (β NS) has been investigated in 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water at 25°C. The reaction follows second order, first order in each reactant. The effect of solvent composition on the rate is significant that the decrease in polarity of the medium decreases the reaction rate. A mechanism involving the formation of zwitterionic addition complex in a fast equilibrium step followed by its conversion into the product by a slow step has been proposed. Evaluation of the equilibrium constant for the formation of zwitterion indicates that the kinetics is not Michaelis-Menten type and the rate law is $k_{obs} = K_1 k_c [\text{PhSH}]$. Kinetics of triethylamine (TEA) catalysed nucleophilic addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene has also been studied in 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water at 25°C. The rate of nucleophilic addition reaction has been considerably increased in the presence of added base. The reaction follows first order in [β -nitrostyrene] and [thiophenol] but fractional order (0.769) in [TEA]. The rate of the reaction is found to increase with decrease in polarity of the medium. The plot of $k_{obs}/[\text{PhSH}]$ versus [TEA] gives a straight line with a definite intercept which indicates the presence of non-catalytic route along with catalytic route. On the basis of kinetic results, a stepwise mechanism involving the formation of zwitterion with PhSH and β NS and a complex with the zwitterion and TEA in equilibrium steps followed by their conversion into the product has been invoked. From the rate law derived both catalytic (k_b) and non-catalytic (k) rate constants are evaluated.

Addition of anionic or neutral nucleophiles to activated olefins is an important class of reaction. The activating groups are normally electron acceptors, which act to stabilize the intermediate carbanion in the stepwise pathways¹⁻⁴. The addition reactions of amine nucleophiles to olefins containing activating groups have been extensively studied⁵⁻⁸. The addition of thiols or thiolate ion to activated double bonds is limited⁹ and is of particular interest because of its relevance to biochemical systems¹⁰. Thiolate ions are found to be more reactive than primary amines^{11,12}. In all nucleophilic addition reactions the formation of carbanion or zwitterion has been proposed as intermediate and the intermediate is largely stabilized by the polar effect of the solvent medium. Mechanistic change has been observed in the addition of amines to β -nitrostyrene when the polarity of the medium is varied^{5,8,13}. Hence it is thought of interest to study the addition reaction of thiophenol (PhSH) to β -nitrostyrene (β NS) in aqueous acetonitrile of various compositions and to find out the reactivity of thiophenol in the presence of a base, triethylamine, which does not add on β -nitrostyrene under the reaction conditions.

Results and discussion

Effect of [β -nitrostyrene] and [thiophenol] on the reaction rate :

The rates of addition reaction of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene was followed under pseudo-first order condition by monitoring the disappearance of UV absorption spectrophotometrically in 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture at 25°C. The plot of log (OD) versus time is linear ($r = 0.999$) showing first-order dependence on [β -nitrostyrene]. The rates of addition reactions were measured at various initial [β NS] (Table 1). Analysis of rate data in Table 1 indicates that the variation of [β NS] at constant [PhSH] does not alter the pseudo-first order rate constants, confirming the first-order dependence on the [β -nitrostyrene]. The effect of [PhSH] on the rate of addition reaction was studied by varying [PhSH] keeping other factors as constants (Table 1). The plot of log k_{obs} versus log [PhSH] is linear with a slope of 1.03 ($r = 0.999$) which indicates that the order of thiophenol is unity.

Effect of solvent on the reaction rate :

The effect of the polarity of the medium on the rate of

^ψDedicated to Professor Y. K. Gupta on his 80th birth anniversary.

Table 4. Equilibrium constant (K_1) and decomposition rate constant (k_c) for the addition reaction at various temperatures in 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture

Temp. (°C)	25	30	35	40
$k_2 = K_1 k_c$, dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	0.284	0.325	0.360	0.383
K_1 , dm ³ mol ⁻¹	108	105	98.9	92.9
$10^3 k_c$, s ⁻¹	2.63	3.10	3.64	4.14

Eq. (3) explains the observed results in the present study. By making use of the relationship $k_{obs}/[PhSH] = K_1 k_c$, k_c values are obtained and are presented in Table 4. Thermodynamic activation parameters, E_a , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are evaluated from the k_c values in Table 4 and are found to be 21.2 kJ mol⁻¹, 18.7 kJ mol⁻¹ and -231 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ respectively. Entropy of activation is large negative for the nucleophilic addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene in 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture at 25°C. This value is much higher than the value observed ($\Delta S^\ddagger = -68.9$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹) for the same reaction in 50% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture⁹ at 25°C. These values are related to the rearrangement of zwitterion to form a neutral product in the second rate limiting step. Therefore in the transition state the separated charges will be partially neutralized when there is a transfer of proton from sulphur to β -carbon atom. This low-polar transition state will be more solvated by less polar solvent medium (80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water) whereas the more polar solvent medium (50% (v/v) acetonitrile-water) may not interact readily with the transition state to this extent. Hence, ΔS^\ddagger is much larger for less polar medium. In the present study, energy of activation is very low ($E_a = 21.2$ kJ mol⁻¹), which is due to larger solvation of the transition state by the less polar solvent medium.

Addition reaction of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene in the presence of amine :

The nucleophilic addition reaction of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene has been studied in the presence of triethylamine (TEA) under identical conditions at 25°C. The reaction follows first order with respect to $[\beta NS]$ which is revealed by a linear plot of $\log [OD]$ versus time ($r = 0.999$). The variation of $[\beta NS]$ shows no appreciable change in the observed first order rate constants (Table 5). The rate of addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene in the presence of triethylamine is measured with different initial $[PhSH]$ while other conditions are kept constant and the rate data are given in Table 5. The plot of $\log [k_{obs}]$ versus $\log [PhSH]$ is linear ($r = 0.999$) with a slope 1.01 which shows that the order with respect to $[PhSH]$ is unity. The rate of the reaction was also measured by varying $[TEA]$ keeping other factors constant (Table 6). The rate increases with increase

Table 5. Effect of varying $[\beta$ -nitrostyrene] and [thiophenol] on the rate of addition reaction in the presence of triethylamine at 25°C

[TEA] = 0.5×10^{-4} mol dm ⁻³			
$10^5 [\beta NS]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [PhSH]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹	$k_2 = k_{obs}/[PhSH]$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
6.0	1.0	15.4	–
8.0	1.0	15.9	–
10.0	1.0	16.7	1.67
12.0	1.0	16.6	–
10.0	1.5	24.9	1.65
10.0	2.0	34.1	1.71
10.0	2.5	41.9	1.68

Table 6. Effect of varying $[TEA]$ on the rate of addition reactions at 25°C

[βNS] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm ⁻³ , [$PhSH$] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³		
$10^5 [TEA]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹	$k_2 = k_{obs}/[TEA]$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
5.0	16.7	33.4
10.0	26.2	26.2
15.0	36.9	25.9
20.0	44.1	22.0

in $[TEA]$, but the plot of $\log k_{obs}$ versus $\log [TEA]$ is linear ($r = 0.999$) with a slope of 0.768 and a definite intercept. Further $k_2 = k_{obs}/[TEA]$ is not a constant and it decreases with increase in $[TEA]$ (Table 6). These observations show that the reaction is fractional order with respect to $[TEA]$ and the presence of definite intercept indicates that both non-catalytic and catalytic reactions are taking place simultaneously.

Effect of solvent polarity on the reaction rate :

The effect of solvent polarity on the rate of base catalysed nucleophilic addition reaction was studied by varying water composition in the reaction medium at 25°C (Table 7). The rate of addition reaction increases with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium which is quite contrary to

Table 7. Effect of solvent on the rate of addition reaction in the presence of TEA at 25°C

[βNS] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm ⁻³ , [$PhSH$] = 1.0×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³ , [TEA] = 0.5×10^{-3} mol dm ⁻³	
% CH ₃ CN (v/v)	$10^4 k_{obs}$ s ⁻¹
90	25.3
80	16.7
70	15.0
60	14.0

the observation for the same reaction in the absence of base (Table 2).

The presence of definite intercept in the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\log [\text{TEA}]$ confirms the occurrence of both catalytic and non-catalytic nucleophilic addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene. The non-catalytic route involves the formation of zwitterion intermediate which is favoured by the increase in polarity of the reaction medium. The catalytic route may involve the formation of a complex incorporating the added triethylamine and this complex may be less polar than zwitterion intermediate. This less polar complex will be more solvated by less polar solvent medium and thus the rate of the base catalysed nucleophilic addition reaction will be higher in less polar solvent medium (Table 7). These expectations are well proved by the observed rate ratio between the catalytic and non-catalytic rate constants. This ratio varies from 20 to 2.5 as the solvent composition varies from 90% to 60% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture (Tables 2 and 7).

On the basis of these kinetic results and product analysis the following reaction mechanism has been speculated for base catalysed thiophenol addition to β -nitrostyrene (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Applying steady state approximation for the formation of [Z] and [C], the rate law can be derived as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_1(k_4 + k_3K_2[\text{TEA}])([\text{PhSH}])}{(k_{-1} + k_4 + k_2[\text{TEA}])} \quad (4)$$

Catalytic and non-catalytic rates are separated and eq. (4) is rearranged as

$$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} = \frac{k_1k_4}{k_{-1} + k_4 + k_2[\text{TEA}]} + \frac{k_1k_3K_2[\text{TEA}]}{k_{-1} + k_4 + k_2[\text{TEA}]} \quad (5)$$

The term $k_1k_4/(k_{-1} + k_4)$ represents non-catalytic route rate constant at the zero concentration of TEA i.e. $k = k_1k_4/(k_{-1} + k_4)$ where k is rate constant for non-catalytic route. Generally $k_4 \ll k_{-1}$.

Hence $k = K_1k_4$.

Now eq. (5) can be written as

$$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} = k + \frac{k_1k_3K_2[\text{TEA}]}{k_{-1} + k_2[\text{TEA}]} \quad (6)$$

On rearranging and taking inverse

$$\frac{1}{\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} - k} = \frac{k_{-2}}{k_3k_1} + \frac{1}{k_3K_2K_1[\text{TEA}]} \quad (7)$$

Combination of constants K_1 , K_2 and k_3 will represent the overall pure base catalysed reaction rate constant

$$\frac{1}{\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} - k} = \frac{k_{-2}}{k_3k_1} + \frac{1}{k_b[\text{TEA}]} \quad (8)$$

Since base catalysed addition reaction is a combination of catalytic and non-catalytic route, the overall rate can be represented as

$$\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} = k + k_b[\text{TEA}] \quad (9)$$

Employing eq. (9) and from the plot of $k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{PhSH}]$ versus $[\text{TEA}]$, non-catalytic reaction rate constant, k is computed. Making use of this k in eq. (8) and from the plot of

$\frac{1}{\frac{k_{\text{obs}}}{[\text{PhSH}]} - k}$ versus $1/[\text{TEA}]$, k_b is obtained from the slope.

Further, eq. (6) explains the observed fractional order with respect to $[\text{TEA}]$.

In order to observe the effect of temperature on the rate of base catalysed nucleophilic addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene, the rates were measured for these reactions at various initial concentrations of TEA at different temperatures viz. 25, 30, 35 and 40°C. The rate constants are summarized in Table 8. The k and k_b values are evaluated and given in Table 9. Analysis of rate data in Table 9 indicates that the rate of nucleophilic addition of thiophenol to β -nitrostyrene in the presence of base (k_b) decreases with increase in temperature. This rate constant is a combina-

Table 8. Effect of [TEA] on the rate of addition reaction in the presence of triethylamine at various temperatures

10^4 [TEA] mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$, s ⁻¹			
	25°C	30°C	35°C	40°C
0.5	1.67	1.64	1.76	1.86
1.0	2.62	2.45	2.64	2.65
1.5	3.69	3.25	3.34	3.22
2.0	4.41	3.94	4.05	4.03

tion of steps 1, 2 and 3 (Scheme 2). Step 2 is highly sensitive to temperature and hence the equilibrium constant for this step will decrease significantly with raise in temperature. Even though the third step rate (k_3) increases with increase of temperature, the overall rate constant ($k_b = K_1 K_2 k_3$) decreases with temperature⁶. In the case of non-catalytic route, the temperature effect is not significant for the formation of zwitterion in the first step (*cf.* Table 4). Hence the rate constant for non-catalytic route (k) increases with increase in temperature (Table 9).

Table 9. Rate constants for catalytic (k_b) and non-catalytic (k) routes for the base catalysed addition reaction at various temperatures

Temp. (°C)	25	30	35	40
k , dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	0.775	0.895	1.06	1.17
$10^{-4} k_b$, dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹	1.76	1.47	1.37	1.26

Experimental

β -Nitrostyrene¹⁵ and thiophenol¹⁶ were prepared by literature methods. Triethylamine was rendered free from primary and secondary amine impurities and distilled over sodium. Acetonitrile was dried for one day over P₂O₅, refluxed for 5 h over P₂O₅ and distilled through a fractionating column and the middle fraction (b.p. 82°C) was collected.

Kinetic procedure :

The rate measurements were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ([PhSH] \gg [BNS] and [PhSH] \gg [BNS] \approx [TEA]) in aqueous acetonitrile spectrophotometrically, monitoring the disappearance of UV absorption maxima at 311 nm. Shimadzu Model UV-1601 UV-Visible spectrophotometer was used with quartz cell of 1 cm path length. All the reactions followed first order kinetics as judged by the linearity of the plots of log (absorbance) versus time. From the slope of these plots the pseudo-first order rate coefficients were calculated. The solvent medium

was 80% (v/v) acetonitrile-water mixture unless and otherwise mentioned.

Product analysis :

Equal amounts of β -nitrostyrene and thiophenol were mixed under kinetic conditions and kept overnight. Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the separated solid was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40–60°C). The product was identified as C₆H₅CH(SC₆H₅)CH₂NO₂ from the IR, mass and NMR spectra. The melting point of this product was 70–71°C (lit.⁹ 72–73°C). β -Nitrostyrene and thiophenol were also mixed in the presence of triethylamine under kinetic conditions and kept overnight. The product was isolated by the usual method and was identified as C₆H₅CH(SC₆H₅)CH₂NO₂.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A.S.) thanks the U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of Emeritus Fellowship. Also the author (P.A.S) is grateful to U.G.C. for permitting him to work under UGC-FIP programme. Thanks are due to the Managing Board of VIINSN College, Virudhunagar for providing research facilities.

References

1. C. F. Bernasconi, D. F. Schuck, R. J. Ketner, M. Weins and Z. Rappoport, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 764.
2. X. Chen and Z. Rappoport, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 5684.
3. H. K. Oh, J. H. Yang, H. W. Lee and I. Lee, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 2188.
4. C. F. Bernasconi and R. B. Killion (Jr), *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 2878.
5. C. F. Bernasconi, *Tetrahedron*, 1989, **45**, 4017.
6. A. F. Popov, I. F. Perepichka and L. I. Kostenko, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1989, 395.
7. A. Shunmugasundaram, T. Lekshmana Thanulingam and R. Murugesan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1991, **31**, 609.
8. H. K. Oh, J. H. Yang, D. D. Sung and I. Lee, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 2000, 101.
9. K. Ananthakumari, A. Sarathi, C. Gnanasekaran and A. Shunmugasundaram, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **42**, 1943.
10. L. Maggiora, R. T. O. Chang, P. F. Tosrence and M. P. Mertes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 3192.
11. M. Rosenberg, S. Balaz, E. Sturdik and A. Kucher, *Collect. Czech Chem Commun.*, 1987, **52**, 425.
12. C. F. Bernasconi and R. B. Killion, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 7506.
13. H. K. Oh, T. S. Kim, H. W. Lee and I. Lee, *J. Chem. Soc.*,

- Perkin Trans.* 2, 2002, 282.
14. D. E. Worrall, "Organic Synthesis", Coll. Vol. I, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1941.
 15. A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., ELBS, 1978.
 16. G. Akerlof, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125.
 17. K. J. Laidler, "Chemical Kinetics", 3rd ed., Harper & Row Publishers, New York, 1987.